

A Study on Dimensions of Women Exploitation

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Reji, K. "A Study on Dimensions of Women Exploitation." *Shanlax Internatioal Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 230–37.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586437>

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Abstract

Human resource is an important element for the development of world economy as well as country's wealth. As human involved in each and every activity, their power is considered to be the best and foremost factor in any corner towards the accomplishment of organized objectives. The power of women directed in terms of developmental forces for achievements. The power in women is everlasting and makes changes in every sphere of life cycle. It is the best weapon to transform the world into holy spot and wisdom. Women step up with the weapons like readiness, acceptance, adoptability, punctuality and spirituality for above all. Today the world faces difficulties in protecting such power in terms of women exploitation. They are exploited in so many ways. This study is for making an understanding on the factors by which women get exploited since inception till life end. Opportunities and advancements for women also viewed as the factors of emergency.

Introduction

Exploitation is the action or fact of treating someone unfairly in order to benefit from their work. Exploitation is everywhere in everyday practice. Starting since marketing to sell any specified product and ending with human life. In our daily living we get affected in many ways. Exploitation spreads like roots of a tree. It sucks human life like mosquitoes. Women are exploited in different ways and it has various dimensions. Violence against women and girls (VAWG) is among the most universal and pervasive human rights violation, affecting at least a billion women across the globe. Recent estimates suggested that approximately 32 percent of women worldwide have experienced physical and sexual violence from their partners or non-partner sexual violence. VAWG takes many forms including physical and emotional abuse, forced and unwanted sex, early and forced marriage, female genital cutting etc.

Violence against women (VAW) also known as gender based violence and sexual and gender based violence (SGBV) are violent acts primarily or exclusively committed against women and girls. Often considered a form of hate crime, this type of violence is gender based, meaning that the acts of violence are committed against women and girls expressly because they are female. The UN declaration on the elimination of violence against women states "violence against women is a manifestation of historically unequal power relations

between men and women” and “violence against women is one of the crucial social mechanisms by which women are forced into a subordinate position compared with men.”

Some main aspects of such exploitation may be highlighted as following:

- Use of women to earn money
- Physical and mental harassment by men in society
- Trafficking of women
- Violence against women

Keywords: Exploitation, human rights, child marriage, differences in work as compared to men.

Review of Literature

Kofi Annan, Secretary General of the United Nations, declared in a 2006 report on the United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) website: Violence against women and girls is a problem of pandemic proportions. At least one out of every three women around the world has been beaten, coerced into sex or otherwise abused in her life time with the abuser usually someone known to her.

The Council of Europe convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence also known as the Istanbul convention provides the following definition of violence against women. “Violence against women” is understood as a violation of human rights and a form of discrimination against women and shall mean all acts of gender based violence that result in or are likely to result in physical, sexual, psychological or economic harm or suffering to women including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty whether occurring in public or in private life.

Several studies have shown a link between poor treatment of women and international violence. These studies show that one of the best predictors of inter- and intra-national violence is the maltreatment of women in the society.

The World Health Organization reports that violence against women puts an undue burden on health care services as women who have suffered violence are more likely to need health services and at higher cost compared to women who have not suffered violence.

According to an article in the Health and Human Rights Journal, regardless of many years of advocacy and involvement of many feminist activist organizations the issue of violence against women still “remains one of the most pervasive forms of human rights violations worldwide.” The violence against women can occur in both public and private spheres of life and at any time of their life span.

ABID GHAFOOR CHAUDHRY conducted a study and describes various forms of VAW in district Toba Tek Singh (Punjab–Pakistan) and some immediate and long-term remedial measures for the proper redressal of violence against women. Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Arid Agriculture, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & BIOLOGY - 1560–8530/2004/06–4–669–671, <http://www.ijab.org>, Violence Against Women – A Case Study.

UNICEF’s report (1997) states that in all societies, poverty, discrimination, ignorance and social unrest are common predictors of violence against women.

Importance of the Study

This study is concerned with the sufferings of women by various anti-social, economic and other forces. Every woman is a pillar for her own nation and is a stone for the world to build it up with culture and discipline. They play multi-dimensional roles like according to stages of development

and situations. They are respectable. Women power is all energy for our mother land. But in real sense, they are not considered as equal with men. Hence the study is conducted to know how the women are affected in exploitation by various forces, causes and ways.

Objectives

- To know the different forms of exploitation against women
- To examine the causes for women exploitation to find out the sources in which exploited women get remedy.
- To evaluate the remedial measures taken towards protection of exploited women.

Research Methodology

The research is based on the secondary data collected from various sources like websites, reports, journals, news papers etc.

Various Forms of Violences Against Women

Crimes against women in India during 2007 – 2016:

Year	Number of Crimes
2007	21
2008	22
2009	23
2010	24
2011	26
2012	28
2013	35
2014	39
2015	37
2016	39

Women experience violence in many ways, from physical abuse to sexual assault and from financial abuse to sexual harassment. Whatever form it takes, violence against women can have serious long-term physical and emotional effects.

- It is found that 35 per cent of women in the world have experiences either physical or sexual intimate partner violence or sexual violence by a non-partner at some point in their lives. studies explored that up to 70% of women suffered physically or mentally from an intimate partner in their lifetime. Because of this increases the rates of depression, having an abortion and acquiring HIV, compared to women in earlier days.

- It is discovered that women who were suffered globally in 2012, almost 50% were killed by intimate partners or family members, compared to less than 6% of men killed in the same year.
- 71% of women and girls in the world affected by various exploitative measures.
- Child marriage is also acting as an important weapon to exploit young women and girls. There are 650 million women and girls get married before the age of 18.
- Among 30 countries in the world, 200 million women and girls alive today underwent female genital mutilation.
- On an average of 15 million adolescent girls in the age group of 15 to 19 worldwide have compelled for forced sex.
- Female students pursuing under-graduation in Universities and other colleges are suffered by sexual harassment.
- In recent five years 39% of women got affected sexually at their workplace.
- Women are struggled sexually, physically and mentally in all walks of their life.

Digital Abuse

Now a-days due to technological advancement, women get affected with the help of digital based parameters. It is more common among younger adults, but it can happen to all women who uses technology, such as smart-phones or computers.

Digital abuse can include

- Frequent unwanted calls or messages
- Harassment by use of social media
- Compulsion to send private pictures
- Insulting and controlling by use of social media
- Wandering your passwords to social media sites and email
- Exploring that you reply right away to texts, emails, and calls.

Word of Records

According to the Commission of inquiry for Women's Report (1997), legislative measures against domestic violence has been enacted in 44 countries around the world, 17 countries have made marital rape, a criminal offense and 27 have passed laws of sexual harassment. Bunch (1977) has quoted few brain storming facts about the status of the women of the world. These include, i) Roughly 60 million women missed because of gender discrimination should be alive today, predominantly in South and West Asia, China and North Africa, ii) In U.S. where overall violent crimes against women have been ever increasing for the past two decades, a woman is physically abused by her intimate partner in every nine seconds, iii) In India - because of dowry problem more than five thousand women killed each year. Most of these not came out and only a very small percentage of murderers are brought to justice.

Natioal Crime Records Bureau

It is recorded in the year 2016 that 39 crimes were reported every hour in India and it was increased from 21 in the year 2007.

Rate of Crime Against Women: Per 100000 Female Population

Crime against women rate was increased from 41.7 in the year 2012 to 55.2 in the year 2016.

CRIME RATE

Case Wise Report: (For Every Hour)

Of all crimes counted 33% of crimes against women were recorded as created by husband and relatives in the year 2016. 11% of crimes resulted by rape of all crimes recorded with 38,947 in the year 2016.

2.5 million crimes against women have been recorded in India over the last decade. It is increased 83% from 1,85,312 in 2007 to 3,38,954 in 2016.

Delhi city had the worst crime rate 182.1 crimes per 1,00,000 women against the national average of 77.2. Delhi reported the highest crime rate of 40.7 in 2016.

Four rape cases reported every hour in 2016 and nine years ago it was recorded two.

Women Crimes

Crime under name	Crime suffer		2016	% variation	
	2014	2015		2014-2015	2015-2016
Total Crimes	38,385	41,001	41,761	6.8%	1.8%

Repor in 2016

SI No	Crime Head	Cases reported	Major Metropolitan Cities During 2016		
1	Cruelty by family members	12218	Delhi 3645	Hyderabad 1311	Jaipur 1008
2	Assault on women on account of her modesty	10458	3746	Mumbai 2183	Bangalore 820
3	Kidnapping & abduction	9256	3364	Mumbai 1142	Bangalore 674
4	Rape	4935	1996	Mumbai 712	Pune 354

Dowry Death Record in India

Year	Number of Death	% Changes (Increase / Decrease)
2011 - 2012	8618 - 8233	(4.5)
2013	8083	(1.8)
2014	8455	4.6
2015	7634	(9.7)
2016	7621	(0.2)

Measures to Address Violence

- Women who suffer with any kind of exploitative measure, they have to rise up and must take the matter to the outer world and try to control the same.
- C-operation among people from all countries is needed to work for the problem of women as each women affected is their own sister. They all must work for the brotherhood life.
- In recent years crimes against women is increasing and this is the situation to change the world. We all need to understand others suffering as it happens to us and keep footsteps towards treatment and betterment.
- Women must be educated well and they must be very much aware of all exploitative forces against them and they must be taught lessons against preventive measures and organization supporting for women upliftment.

Milestones of Prevention

Some of the most important milestones on the international level for the prevention of violence against women include:

- In 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) is adopted.
- In 1993 World Conference on Human Rights is conducted and this is the first human rights conference.
- In 1993 UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly.

- In 1994 International Conference on Population and Development organized to with the intension to reduce the violent forces against women.
- In 1996, the World Health Assembly (WHA) declared violence a major public health issue and it should be chased out from the society.
- This was as per the report of WHO in 2002. The UN also created the Trust Fund to Support Actions to Eliminate Violence Against Women.
- In 2002, World Health Organization published the first world report on Violence and Health and it addresses the almost all major violations against women.
- In 2004, the World Health Organization published its “Multi-country study on Women’s Health and Domestic Violence against Women”, a study conducted with the help of survey over 24000 women in 10 countries and they are from various religions, places. castes and with different cultures.
- The 2011 Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence and this is the second regional legally-binding instrument on violence against women and girls.
- In 2013, the United Nations Commission on the Status of Women (CSW) adopted, by consensus, Agreed Conclusions on the elimination and prevention of all forms of violence against women and girls.
- In 2013, the UN General Assembly passed its first resolution calling for the protection of defenders of women’s human rights. This resolution specifically urges the states to put in place gender-specific laws and policies for the protection of women’s human rights defenders.
- In addition to this all individual countries have organized efforts legally, politically and socially to prevent, reduce and punish victims concerned violence against women.

Findings & Suggestions

Violence against women and girls (VAWG) is among the most universal and pervasive human rights violations, affecting at least a billion women across the globe. In present situation it is increasing than earlier. The Reports and studies made and corrective measures also been undertaken since then it grows day by day. Every woman must be treated as sisters and mothers according to their age group and then the problem of exploitation will go away from us and we will be able to find the world as “God’s Own Land”. Any problem in this matter of women mustl be viewed the problem of human and we all must work for the betterment.

Limitations

This study is limited with the secondary data collected by the researcher and conclusions are drawn on that basis only.

Scope for Future Research

This research provides information to any person who seek information and try for knowledge based content on exploitation of women.

References

1. Deng, G., Vani S. Kulkarni and R. Gaiha (2018) “What factors can explain the rise and inter-state variation in crimes against women in India?” submitted for publication. An earlier version is available as a GDI (Manchester) working paper 2017-15.
2. Belur, J., N. Tilley, N. Daruwalla, M. Kumar, V. Tiwari, D. Osrin (2014) “The social construction of ‘dowry deaths’ ”, *Social Science & Medicine* 119 1-9.

3. ABID GHAFOR CHAUDHRY conducted a study and describes various forms of VAW in district Toba Tek Singh (Punjab–Pakistan) NTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & BIOLOGY - 1560–8530/2004/06–4–669–671, <http://www.ijab.org>, Violence Against Women – A Case Study.
4. <https://www.icrw.org>
5. <https://en.wikipedia.org>
6. www.indiaspend.com
7. www.shutterstock.com
8. www.wikipedia.org
9. <http://ncrb.nic.in>